

**INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM
PRINCIPLES OF APPLICATION****Mirzaev Musurmon Umidullaevich**

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Abstract: Information technologies in the field of tourism, the tourism industry, its outstanding achievements, preservation of historical and cultural objects, modern communication technologies with the development of the Internet, reports of the state statistics Agency.

Keywords: Tourism, tourism industry, information technology, historical and cultural objects and modern communication technologies.

Introduction. According to its economic indicators, the world tourism industry is one of the main profitable industries. The tourism industry is one of the most profitable in the economic system of most countries. The tourism industry is distinguished by outstanding achievements and numerous directions, and also has a strong influence on the transport system and the level of trade between various international relations. It follows from this that the development of the tourism sector affects not only the growth of this sphere, but also the development of international relations, the growth of the transport sector, the preservation of historical and cultural sites, the spread of cultures and many other areas. In the tourism industry, in particular, thanks to the use of information technology and computer systems, you can get such opportunities as convenience, speed, ease, economy, be aware of the news, create new jobs.

At the present stages of tourism development, according to its structure and characteristics, it consists of several components in accordance with the complex of information technologies used:

- ✓ automatic booking system;

- ✓ setting up video systems;
- ✓ coordination of information flows;
- ✓ the system of using various privileged cards;
- ✓ general system of electronic money transfers;
- ✓ cancellation systems before a certain deadline;
- ✓ integration with travel companies, etc.

Modern information technologies are an important component of the tourism industry and continue to determine its dynamic development. The effective functioning of a travel company's website is a key component of any travel agency. The activity of the site is not complete without the help of advertising. Personal computer and Internet, popular modern technologies are the determining factor that more and more information technologies are being introduced into all spheres of tourism. For further modernization and mobilization of the tourism industry, travel companies and various travel agencies use all the possibilities of Internet information resources. For example, online booking has become a powerful factor contributing to the development of tourism within the framework of modern communication technologies with the development of the Internet, allowing you to book tourist trips electronically. The features of online booking allowed airlines to organize tours offered by the company at special prices, as a result of the events held, travel companies experienced significant growth, which is characterized by a high indicator of user interest in this field of tourism. The method of remote booking has become a progressive factor that has changed the entire tourist activity, making it more accessible and modernized [1].

Tour operators are actively using new media in their activities. About 80-90% of all travel agencies in developed countries use an automatic booking method. It is impossible to imagine the management of all actions without the use of computer reservation systems. The online booking system has had a huge impact on the entire tourism industry. Using a computer reservation system allows you to remotely book a hotel, book a hotel room on request, book air tickets, car rental, train tickets and other similar actions. The largest and most common sources of automatic booking are

AMADEUS, Worldspan, Galileo, Sabre, Fidelio and others. their activities are an integral part of the international tourism services market.

Computer systems used in travel companies, depending on their functional characteristics, are divided into three classes [1]:

- ✓ the main technological systems. The principle of their work is based on the guarantee of the fulfillment of consumer orders. In these systems, the operator has access to the main computer systems and analyzes consumer orders;
- ✓ auxiliary systems. The main purpose of auxiliary systems is to automate the creation of documents related to the activities of a travel company. For such documents, you can transfer invoices, create special design tickets;
- ✓ coordination systems that facilitate the updating of information directly related to the company's activities.

Another very big impetus in the development of tourist information was the global Internet. Today, almost all travel companies have access to this network via email. All users of the network use them to get extensive information about tourist services. Government organizations responsible for tourism, private companies, travel agencies, hotels, travel associations, carriers, companies offering services for attractions have large information systems. Posting information on the Internet is usually cheaper than publishing a book or booklet, information changes its appearance easily and quickly, and high-quality color illustrative information can also be transmitted. The information reaches a wide range of users in developed countries [2].

According to the conducted research, more than 60% of the services provided via the Internet in the United States are in the field of tourism services. The demand in the tourism sector depends on the price, therefore, search queries concerning the requested information often play a decisive role, since consumers prefer to search and book tickets and hotels on the Internet for any other source of information [1].

Uzbekistan has also established a customer service system through computer booking of travel agencies, where hotel room booking services are mainly used, there are also travel agencies that book air tickets, train tickets online, but online booking is

carried out mainly in individual cases, that is, in accordance with the wishes of persons wishing to travel on a separate route, while in ordinary species this is not the case. Currently, people with sufficient knowledge in the field of information technology also have the opportunity to book online directly from websites. In any case, booking air tickets, train tickets, hotels, various services using online booking systems will lead to growth in the tourism sector.

According to the State Statistics Agency, from January to December 2022, 5.2 million foreign citizens visited Uzbekistan for tourist purposes. It is noted that this indicator compared to the corresponding period last year amounted to 3.4 million per person or 2.8 times [2].

Summing up, we can say that as the interest of foreign citizens in Uzbekistan in the field of tourism grows, the integration of Uzbek travel companies into world travel agencies through modern information technologies, Internet systems, services will lead to the further development of the tourism industry of Uzbekistan, the growth of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Literature:

1. M.A. Mirzayev. Fundamentals of Tourism: textbook for undergraduate students / O ' Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T.: Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan, 2011.

2. <https://xabardor.uz/uz/post>.